

Forest fire effects on sediment connectivity in headwater sub-catchments: Evaluation of indices performance

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HIGHLIGHTS

- The IC-Borselli and AIC approaches are sensitive to the fire effects on SC.
- The overlay between the fire severities and the geomorphic features is a key aspect.
- The SC_{OUTLET} maps predict lower SC than the SC_{STREAM} maps except in the outlet.
- A positive agreement appears between the sediment yield and the changes in SC.
- SC_{STREAM} simulations are recommended to place sediment control measures on hillslopes.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Forest fires and post-fire practices influence the hydrological response of the soil in terms of runoff and sediment connectivity (SC). In this study, the ability of four indices (IC-Borselli, IC-Cavalli, IC-Persichillo and aggregated index of connectivity (AIC)) to assess SC was evaluated in three Mediterranean headwater sub-catchments (66, 143 and 194 ha) affected by an arson fire in 2012. Three temporal scenarios (before the fire, one year after the fire and two years after the fire including post-fire practices (salvage logging, skid trails and check dams)) and two computation targets (streams: hillslope–channel SC; and check–dams: hillslope–outlet SC) were considered, obtaining 66 maps of SC at fine spatial resolution (2 m of cell size). Burn severity classes were estimated using Landsat-7 imagery and the dNBR index. The indices' output analysis included geomorphic (landscape units), mathematic (significance, percentiles and frequency distribution), fire (burn severity classes and unburnt areas) and sedimentological (measured specific sediment yield – SSY) criteria. The IC-Borselli and AIC were the most responsive approaches to the effects of fire on SC at catchment scale, whereas the IC-Persichillo was the most sensitive index to the increasing burn severities. The overlay between the fire severities and the geomorphic features appeared as a key aspect to understand the hydrological response at both the stream-system and outlet targets. We found a good and positive agreement between the measured SSY in the three check-dams and the changes in the estimated SC_{OUTLET} due to the fire, especially with the IC-Borselli and AIC. For a better implementation of post-fire programs, we recommend SC_{OUTLET} maps –from AIC– to assess sediment transport in streams, which is dominated by the deposition process, and SC_{STREAM} maps –from IC-Borselli and AIC– to place sediment control measures at hillslopes for intense rainfall events when effective sediment transport happens.

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1. Introduction

Forest fires modify short- and long-term natural dynamic –patterns and magnitude– of the hydrological response of the soil, including soil permeability, runoff, soil erosion, sediment delivery and transport of pollutants (Vieira et al., 2018; Yu et al., 2019). The role of vegetation type, fire intensity and human activities (land uses and post-fire management) is important in determining how much the hydrological condition of a system will react (Carracedo et al., 2018; Foster et al., 2019). Currently, there is an interest on the scientific society of linking fire dynamics, the effects of fire on soils and particle transport, fire-risk management and post-fire practices (Albert-Belda et al., 2019; Lucas-Borja et al., 2019) in order to bring solutions to the on-site and off-site consequences of fires (FIRElinks, 2019).

The term “hydrologic connectivity”, which was originated in ecology (Pringle, 2001), refers to water-mediated transfer of matter, energy and/or organisms within or between elements of the hydrologic cycle. The term “sediment connectivity” was initially used in river-channel systems for understanding the linkages between river reaches, the influence of sediment sources on channel morphology and the mechanisms and liability to propagation of morphological change (Hooke, 2003). This concept was rapidly applied in sediment delivery studies at catchment scale to assess how the spatial pattern of surface characteristics (e.g., topography, vegetation, rock fragment cover, crusts) influences runoff distance and connectivity on a hillslope (de Vente et al., 2006). In the last decade, the concept of “runoff and sediment connectivity” (SC), considered as an emergent property of the system state reflecting the continuity and strength of runoff and sediment pathways at a given point in time (Heckmann et al., 2018), has gained increasing interest in the earth sciences community (Cavalli et al., 2019). In general, SC has been understood as the degree of coupling/decoupling between different parts of a system (Cavalli et al., 2013; Harvey, 2001) due to processes acting and interacting at different spatio-temporal scales (Cerdà et al., 2013).

Soil and topographic properties, vegetation type and patterns and streams of a system (catchment, landscape) control the processes of water- and sediment-transfer and comprise the structural connectivity. The way the structural connectivity evolves through time at a specific spatio-temporal scale represents the functional connectivity (Nunes et al., 2018). The natural dynamic of SC is clearly modified by human activities, such as croplands and sub-urban areas, showing a different and more complex response owing to changing inputs (Poesen, 2018). Disconnectivity concerns features or processes that are too remote from each other in space or time, so that a change in one component or process does not influence another (Wohl et al., 2019).

Although SC offers a suitable conceptual framework for geomorphic studies, still there is not a consensus on how to calculate and to compare connectivity quantitatively at different spatial and temporal scales and among distinct landscapes (Wohl, 2017). Wohl et al. (2019) provided a list of diverse indicators and approaches to measure SC at different scales and capturing landscape heterogeneity and connectivity patterns. This list included the use of graph and network theory metrics, indices and numerical modelling. Indices output are dimensionless indicators that assess the probability that overland flow arrives at a user-defined target, including sinks or channels, in such a way that output values are a function of the computation target (Crema and Cavalli, 2018).

In addition to vegetation removal, forest fires affect soil properties causing a reduction of soil aggregate stability and an increase of water repellency, all of them leading into changes on soil surface processes (e.g., surface runoff and soil erosion) (Stavi, 2019). Post-fire management practices (salvage logging, skid trails and check-dams), natural vegetation regrowth and/or afforestation seek to minimize soil erosion and runoff and sediment yield, favour vegetation recovery and therefore decrease connectivity (Martínez-Murillo and López-Vicente, 2018; González-Romero et al., 2019). Despite the available literature about fire-affected areas and approaches to assess SC, there is no default

method nor universal metric to quantify SC changes in fire-affected headwater areas. Knowing how existing connectivity indices are able to capture these changes is a non-solved research line in this topic. This study aims to identify the least and most responsive approach to assess fire-induced changes on sediment connectivity in mountainous areas. We evaluated the performance of four indices to map SC at three temporal scenarios (before, just after and several years after the fire) in three headwater Mediterranean sub-catchments with similar physiographic characteristics. Two different computation targets, the stream system and check-dam of each sub-catchment, were chosen to assess hillslope–channel and hillslope–outlet SC, respectively. All estimations were analysed using field observations and measurements, namely: I) geomorphic features (the study area has marked landscape changes), II) burn severity classes (using satellite imagery) and III) calculated values of specific sediment yield in the three check-dams. The mathematical analysis of the spatial distribution of the SC values (percentiles and frequency distribution) and temporal changes of all metrics was added to the results analysis.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Forest fire and temporal scenarios

An arson fire started in July 1st, 2012 and lasted ca. 24 h. Despite the short duration, the total burned area reached 5500 ha and affected numerous headwater areas in the Sierra de Los Donceles, in the provinces of Albacete and Murcia (south-eastern Spain) (Fig. 1a,b). On average, this landscape suffered a moderate-high fire severity, according to the fire severity classes proposed by Key and Benson (2005) and estimated using satellite imagery (Gómez-Sánchez et al., 2017). However, clear changes on fire severity were observed along the burned surface (Fig. 1c; Table 1).

Three temporal scenarios were defined from the date of the fire: I) the “Pre-Fire” scenario, from July 1, 2011 to June 30, 2012; II) the “Fire” scenario, from July 1, 2012 to June 30, 2013; during this period no post-fire management activities were done, and thus, it represents the sole effects of the fire on vegetation. And III) the “Post-Fire” scenario, from July 1, 2014 to June 30, 2015; during this period, the post-fire practices (salvage logging, skid trails and check-dams) and incipient natural vegetation recovery were included in the computation of SC. No afforestation has been done in this area after the fire. Each scenario lasts one year, and started and ended in the same day of the year.

2.2. Study area

Three headwater sub-catchments were selected within the fire-affected area that are called Palomar (Sc.Pal), Rayares#2 (Sc.Ray) and Conejo#5 (Sc.Con) (Fig. 1). The sub-catchment area and mean slope gradient range between 66 and 194 ha and between 38% and 47%, respectively. The basin elongation ratio (diameter of a circle of the same area as the basin to the maximum basin length) ranges between 0.60 (elongated type) and 0.71 (less elongated type); and the maximum basin length ranges between 1483 and 2256 m (Table 1) (more details about the use of catchment shape indices in López-Vicente et al., 2009). The ephemeral streams are only active during intense and/or long-lasting rainfall events. Under these similar topographic conditions, comparable peak flow discharges are expected at a given rainfall duration (Kumar, 2011) and thus the selected sub-catchments are comparable. Before the fire, the main land use at the burned area was an open conifer forest of *Pinus halepensis* M. and a rich shrub and herbaceous layer. Among these companion species, shrubs such as *Quercus coccifera* L. and *Pistacia lentiscus* L., dwarf shrubs like *Rosmarinus officinalis* L., *Lavandula latifolia* Med. or *Thymus vulgaris* L. and perennial grasses as *Macrochloa tenacissima* L. or *Brachypodium retusum* (Pers.) P.Beauv. were common (Sup. Fig. 1). Regarding the studied sub-catchments, this open conifer forest was dominant at Sc.Pal, meanwhile the shrub

Fig. 1. Location of the study area within the Iberian Peninsula and selected headwater sub-catchments in the “Sierra de Los Donceles” in the area affected by the wildfire (a). Pictures of the study area before and after the forest fire (b). Map of the burn severity (c) and picture of one check-dam built as part of the post-fire management practices (d).

and herbaceous layer occupied a larger area at Sc.Ray and Sc.Con (Table 1). After the fire, a homogeneous recovery of the shrub and herbaceous layer –with pioneer Mediterranean species– with incipient pine regeneration in some of the slopes was observed in the three sub-catchments (Sup. Fig. 2).

The climate in this area is semi-arid Mediterranean with an average annual rainfall depth of ca. 320 mm and temperature of 16.2 °C (1990–2014; source: AEMET; Spanish Agency of Meteorology). Most rainfall, ca. 86%, was recorded in two periods, between September and November and between February and April. Summers are typically

Table 1
Main physiographic characteristics of the three sub-catchments, including the area occupied by the main land uses before the wildfire (Pre-Fire scenario).

Sub-catchment (ID)	Area (ha)	Elongation Ratio	Slope %	Streams (m)	Soil permeability Class	Fire severity Class	Forest (ha)	Scrubland (ha)	Pasture (ha)	Arable land (ha)	Bare soil (ha)	Trail (ha)	Other ^a (ha)
Sc.Pal	194	0.71	37.6	16,325	Low	Moderate-High	74.4	66.1	45.9	2.7	3.7	0.8	ND
Sc.Ray	66	0.62	46.7	8482	High	Moderate-High	12.4	19.8	30.8	0.5	0.6	0.3	1.5
Sc.Con	143	0.60	41.5	14,199	Medium-High	Moderate-High	46.9	52.5	36.0	3.5	3.8	0.7	ND

^a Urban soil.

dry and hot. During the three evaluated scenarios, the total rainfall depth and average intensity were of 200, 444 and 411 mm and 1.9, 2.7 and 3.6 mm h⁻¹, during the Pre-Fire, Fire and Post-Fire scenarios, respectively. The predominant parent materials are Jurassic bedrocks at the upper areas (dolomites, dolomitic limestones and conglomerates). At the lower parts, Quaternary colluviums prevail. Soils have a sandy clay loam texture and were classified as Inceptisols and Aridisols according to the USDA Soil Taxonomy (USDA, 1999). Soil permeability varies between medium and very high, based on the data provided by the Spanish Geological Survey (IGME). The existing channels of this area are narrow (10–20 m wide) with steep stream-banks.

2.3. Fire image acquisition, processing and burn severity assessment

The burn severity assessment was carried out following the methodology described by Gómez-Sánchez et al. (2017). Two Landsat-7 images per scenario pre-fire (07/08/2011; 08/09/2011) and immediately post-fire (08/07/2012; 09/08/2012), were acquired from the United States Geological Survey (USGS) Global Visualization Viewer. A radiometric correction by gap filling was applied (Rodríguez-Ramos et al., 2009) as well as the reflectance calculus and a FLAASH (Fast Line-of-Sight Atmospheric Analysis of Spectral Hypercubes) atmospheric correction (Adler-Golden et al., 1999). The satellite imagery had a pixel size of 30 × 30 m and 15 × 15 m for the multispectral and panchromatic bands, respectively.

The map of the burn severity was generated by means of the Normalized Burn Ratio (NBR). This index highlights burned areas indicating the severity of burn (Key and Benson, 2005). The NBR calculates the distinct responses of bands 4 (Near Infrared, NIR, 0.64–0.67 μm) and 6 (Short-wave Infrared, SWIR, 1.57–1.65 μm), which reflect changes in soil and vegetation moisture (García and Caselles, 1991):

$$NBR = \frac{NIR - SWIR}{NIR + SWIR} \quad (1)$$

The NBR ratio was calculated for both pre and post-fire scenarios. Then, the scaled index of burn severity, called differenced Normalised Burn Ratio (dNBR) (Key and Benson, 2005; Escuin et al., 2008), was calculated with the equation:

$$dNBR = NBR_{pre} - NBR_{post} \quad (2)$$

The dNBR values were categorised using the classification of the USGS FIREMON program (USGS, 2004) (Sup. Table 1). As regards how these dNBR values are related with the field, unburned areas usually have values close to zero, due to the lack of differences between scenarios. On the contrary severely burned areas will be likely to have higher positive values. The moderate-high severity class was the most frequent class in the three sub-catchments. However, some differences were observed between them. The highest variability was found in Sc.Pal, with small unburned areas and the largest area under high severity. The whole surface of the other two sub-catchments was burned, although high severity affected a larger area in Sc.Con than in Sc.Ray.

Once the categories were defined, a supervised classification method using a minimal distance algorithm was applied to classify each pixel (Chuvieco, 2010). A total of 122 field plots were systematically established. Randomly, 44 plots were used as training sites for the classification algorithm and the remaining 78 plots were used to validate the results. The statistical analysis was carried out by calculating the confusion matrix and the Kappa statistic, which allowed us to know if the accuracy of our classification was high (values close to 1) or not (values close to 0). The overall accuracy of the predicted values given by the confusion matrix was of the 78.57% and the Kappa statistic was 0.6889.

2.4. Indices of runoff and sediment connectivity

In this study, we used four indices of SC: I) the equation proposed by Borselli et al. (2008) with the updates used by Ortíz-Rodríguez et al. (2019) regarding the flow accumulation algorithm and maximum slope gradient (called in this study IC-B2019); II) the adapted version of IC for mountainous areas proposed by Cavalli et al. (2013) and enhanced by Trevisani and Cavalli (2016) (IC-C2016); III) an adapted version of IC-C2016 to represent the impedance to water flow related to each land use and based on the Overland Flow Manning's *n* Roughness Values, proposed by Persichillo et al. (2018) (IC-P); and IV) the aggregated index of SC (AIC) proposed by López-Vicente and Ben-Salem (2019). As vegetation and topography factors change over time, and particularly due to the fire and post-fire practices, the four approaches estimate structural SC within the same scenario and assess functional SC when the different temporal scenarios are evaluated with the same index. However, the number of inputs of each index differs, and thus, their potential response to the temporal changes in the system (Sup. Table 2). The four indices are defined in the range of $[-\infty, +\infty]$ and connectivity increases when the index grows toward $+\infty$.

The original index proposed by Borselli et al. (2008) accounts for the role played by the drainage area and flow path characteristics at each pixel. The downslope module (D_{dn}) assesses the probability that overland flow arrives at a defined sink or stream system along the flow path. The upslope module (D_{up}) estimates the potential for downward routing of overland flow occurring upslope and also implements a “stream power”-like approach, accounting the average values of the evaluated properties in the drainage area:

$$IC_K = \log_{10} \left(\frac{D_{up,K}}{D_{dn,K}} \right) = \log_{10} \left(\frac{\overline{W}_K \cdot \overline{S}_K \cdot \sqrt{A_K}}{\sum_{i=K,n_K} \frac{d_i}{W_i \cdot S_i}} \right) \quad (3)$$

where A (m²) is the upslope drainage area, \overline{W} (dimensionless) is the average weighing factor of A , \overline{S} (m/m) is the average slope gradient of A , d_i (m) is the length of the *i*th cell along the downslope path, W_i (dimensionless) is the weight of the *i*th cell, and S_i (m/m) is the slope gradient of the *i*th cell. The subscript K indicates that each cell i has its own IC value.

The weighting factor W is used to calculate the impedance to runoff and sediment fluxes due to the characteristics of the ground and land uses. For many authors (e.g. Borselli et al., 2008; Sougnez et al., 2011; Vigiak et al., 2012; Schneider et al., 2013; de Walque et al., 2017; Singh et al., 2017), the W factor of Eq. (3) is equal to the C-factor (cover-management) of the RUSLE (Renard et al., 1997) and RUSLE2 (USDA, 2008) soil erosion model. This factor enables to model the effect of tillage practices and vegetation management –in cropland and woodland– on the soil loss rates. In Eq. (3), slope gradient of <0.005 must be adjusted to $S_i = 0.005$ and higher than 1 must be set to a maximum value of $S_i = 1$. In the original approach, the weighted flow path length and the \overline{W} , \overline{S} and A factors were calculated with the D8 single-flow algorithm. However, in a recent study Eq. (3) was run using the D-Infinity algorithm (see Ortíz-Rodríguez et al., 2019). Thus, we chose this algorithm to run the IC-B2019.

Cavalli et al. (2013) and Crema and Cavalli (2018) adapted the W factor for landscapes with homogeneous land uses (mainly alpine areas) and applied the IC equation using the topographic roughness index (RI). They also introduced changes regarding the flow accumulation algorithm and maximum slope threshold. The RI refers to the residual irregularity resulting from subtracting a moving average over 5×5 cells of a DEM from the original DEM region:

$$RI = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^{25} (X_i - X_m)^2}{25}} \quad (4)$$

where X_i is the original DEM value and X_m is the pixel value in the moving window. An inverse relationship exists between the RI and IC : Lower connectivity has higher RI values, because ground irregularities limit sediment transport. Therefore, the inverse normalization of the RI values is necessary to obtain the W factor:

$$W = RI_N = 1 - \left(\frac{RI}{RI_{max}} \right) \quad (5)$$

where RI_{max} is the maximum RI value in the evaluated catchment.

Later, Trevisani and Cavalli (2016) found that Eqs. (4) and (5) favoured a skewed distribution of the RI_N values with a small range of variation that packed toward a weighting factor of 1. These authors proposed normalizing the natural logarithm of RI_N :

$$W = RI_{NLn} = 1 - \left(\frac{\ln(RI) - \ln(RI_{min})}{\ln(RI_{max}) - \ln(RI_{min})} \right) \quad (6)$$

where the minimum RI values are trimmed to 0.001. These authors adopted the D-infinity flow accumulation algorithm to compute the flow path length and the weighted upslope factors. This algorithm is available in the software SAGA© 2.1.2 64 bit (Conrad et al., 2015) and better captures the actual flow paths on hillslopes where divergent flow predominates and provides a better approximation of channel width by partitioning flow over the entire cross section (López-Vicente et al., 2014).

Persichillo et al. (2018) proposed to use the overland flow Manning's n roughness values to model the impedance to overland flow (W factor). When the hydraulic parameters of Manning's equation are not available, it is possible to estimate the n roughness value of the different land uses using available tables. The Manning's coefficients are used as input in event-based hydrological models to improve runoff predictions, such as Lefrancq et al. (2017) did in headwater catchments with LISEM model; and Wang and Yang (2018) did in a large Chinese basin with HiPIMS model. Persichillo et al. (2018) kept the modifications made by Cavalli et al. (2013) regarding the flow accumulation algorithm and maximum slope threshold. In particular, the n values represent the friction applied to the flow by the channel or soil surface. Therefore, the W factor was extracted using the following equation:

$$W = 1 - n \quad (7)$$

More recently, López-Vicente and Ben-Salem (2019) developed the aggregated index of runoff and sediment connectivity (AIC). This index is based on the original Borselli's et al. (2008) index, takes up some of the modifications made by Cavalli et al. (2013) and includes new factors related to the residual topography, rainfall erosivity and soil permeability. The AIC allows study spatial and temporal dynamics of SC at (large) catchment scale:

$$AIC_k = \log_{10} \left(\frac{D_{up,k}}{D_{dn,k}} \right) = \log_{10} \left(\frac{\overline{R_t} \cdot \overline{RT} \cdot \overline{C_t} \cdot \overline{K_p} \cdot \overline{S} \cdot \sqrt{A_k}}{\sum_{k=i}^n \frac{d_i}{AWC_i}} \right) \quad (8)$$

$$AWC_i = R_{ti} \cdot RT_i \cdot C_{ti} \cdot K_{pi} \cdot S_i \quad (9)$$

where AWC is the aggregated weighting factor at catchment scale, R_t is the normalized rainfall erosivity factor for the period t (values between 0 and 1), RT is the residual topography factor (normalized values between 0 and 1), C_t is the C-RUSLE factor for the period t (values between 0 and 1), K_p is the soil permeability factor (normalized values between 0 and 1) and S is the slope gradient (m/m). The K_p factor considers the influence of the soil physical properties on the sediment connectivity because the values of soil water infiltration and retention capacity significantly vary at large spatial scale (Liu et al., 2019). Rainfall erosivity, EI_{30t} , is computed at monthly scale as the sum of the rainfall

erosivities at event scale:

$$EI_{30} = (E)(I_{30}) = \left(\sum_{k=1}^m e_r \Delta V_r \right) I_{30} \quad (10)$$

where m (n) is the number of temporal intervals established for each storm; e_r (MJ/ha mm) is the kinetic energy of a storm for the r period; ΔV_r (mm) is the volume of rainfall registered during the r period; and I_{30} (mm/h) is the maximum rainfall intensity of each storm. In Eq. (10), EI_{30t} values lower than 0.01 must be adjusted to $EI_{30t} = 0.01$ in order to avoid computational errors. The kinetic energy is assessed as follows:

$$e_r = 0.29[1 - 0.72 \exp(-0.082i_r)] \quad (11)$$

$$i_r = \frac{\Delta V_r}{\Delta t_r} \quad (12)$$

where i_r (mm/h) is the rainfall intensity for the r period; and Δt_r (min) is the duration of the r period. When the temporal subscript t in Eqs. (8) and (9) is equal to one average year, the values and maps represent the structural SC (AIC_{ST}). When this subscript is equal to a specific month, week or runoff event, the values and maps reflect the dynamic processes of functional SC (AIC_{FN}).

2.5. Input data, computation targets and metrics

Two LiDAR-based digital elevation models (DEMs) were generated at 2×2 m of grid cell size by using the free available point cloud data obtained in 2009 (before the fire) and 2016 (after the fire and post-fire management practices) by the Spanish National Centre of Geographic Information (IGN) and executing several tools of *LAStools* and *ArcGIS© 10.3* software. Before computing the indices, the Planchon and Darboux algorithm (available in SAGA© 2.1.2 64 bit) was used to remove the small local depressions (artifacts) without adding unrepresentative flat surfaces. A minimum gradient of 0.01° was used to ensure flow routing across the filled sinks. Then, the boundary of the upslope contributing area of each sub-catchment was calculated from the location of the check-dam upwards using the flow accumulation map. The roughness index, RI in Eq. (4), was estimated using the DEMs and the 'Residual Analysis (Grid)' tool (SAGA© 2.1.2 64 bit), with a radius of 2 cells –including the centre cell– that created a 5×5 moving average window. The standard deviation of the slope gradient (SSD) was calculated with the same tool and the residual topography factor, RT in Eq. (9), was obtained as the normalized and inverse values of SSD. A minimum RT value of 0.001 was set to avoid computational errors.

Two land use and land cover (LULC) maps (year 2011: prior to the fire; and 2014: two years after the fire with incipient vegetation recovery) were freely obtained from the IGN (SIOSE system of classification; at 1:25,000). Although these maps are accurate, we modified them in order to ensure the inclusion of two important landscape features: I) the trails; and II) the narrow and very steep areas of bare soil in the banks of the gullies. Each SIOSE land cover polygon is a combination of several land uses, such as "open pine forest (50%) with presence of shrubs (30%) and herbs (20%)", with different percentages associated to each land use. The LULC maps included attributes on land use category, C-factors (soil erosion component), and Manning's n roughness values (overland flow component) (Sup. Table 3).

The annual RUSLE C-factors for the land uses of the Pre-Fire (14 land cover types) and Post-Fire (15 land cover types) scenarios were calculated using the harmonized values proposed by Panagos et al. (2015) in a review article made for the 28 countries of the European Union. The C-RUSLE map of the Fire scenario was obtained by multiplying the Pre-Fire C-RUSLE map with the weighted map of burn severity classes and the weighting values proposed by Larsen and MacDonald (2007) and Yochum and Norman (2015): low burn = 1.10, moderate burn

= 2.25 and high burn = 3.75. Although [Martínez-Murillo and López-Vicente \(2018\)](#) successfully used this approach to estimate C-factors in a Mediterranean mountainous fire-affected area, we modified these ratios to obtain C-factors in the same range as those reported by [Panagos et al. \(2015\)](#) for areas affected by recent fires, with a maximum C-factor value of 0.55 (Table 2). The Manning's n roughness values of the different land covers of the Pre-Fire and Post-Fire scenarios were estimated using the tables proposed by [Chow \(1959\)](#). The Manning's n values for the Fire scenario were calculated using the burn severity map and the approach of [Moody and Kinner \(2006\)](#) who suggested that fire basically results in n values near that of bare soil (0.011). We only used the n value of bare soil for the areas affected by the highest burn severity whereas the other fire-affected areas had progressive values between that of bare soil and those of the original n values before the fire.

The rainfall erosivity factor, R_f in Eq. (9), of each temporal scenario was obtained by using the precipitation records, every 5 min, from the "Cenajo" weather station that is located near the study area (data source: CHSegura-SAIH; code 04A02P01) (Table 2). The soil permeability factor, K_p in Eq. (9), was obtained using the map of lithostratigraphic units (source: IGME; at 1:50,000). The lowest value ($K_p = 0.333$) was assigned to the unit with very high permeability and moderate ($K_p = 0.667$) and higher ($K_p = 1$) values corresponded to the units with high and moderate permeability, respectively.

The presence of water in the stream systems is ephemeral and it is mainly controlled by the occurrence of intense rainfall events. In the eastern part of the Iberian Peninsula heavy rainfall events with return periods of under three years cause significant sediment loads ([Taguas et al., 2013](#)). Thus, we decided to run the four indices using two different computation targets: I) the stream systems, as representative of sediment delivery during short and intense episodes (SC_{STREAM}); and II) the outlet, as representative of the medium- and long-term processes of sediment transport (SC_{OUTLET}). The difference between the SC_{STREAM} and SC_{OUTLET} computation is based on the Flow-Direction map. Those pixels that are considered the target of the SC assessment have a value of Flow-Direction equals to zero. Thus, two masks were generated with GIS software to modify the original map of Flow-Direction: The 'outlet-target' and 'stream-target' masks. These changes do not affect the general SC Eq. (3) and only affect the computation of the downslope component (D_{dm}). According to [Crema and Cavalli \(2018\)](#), a sink introduces a feature that is acting as sink toward sediment fluxes. The choice of this option needs to be corroborated by the presence of features such as lakes and ponds, dams or morphologic barriers and buffers that have an active role in decoupling part of the catchment. In this way, the characterization of the sediment dynamics is limited to a more realistic boundary expressing the effective catchment area. In this study, we considered the non-silted check-dams as effective sediment sinks.

Taking into account the indices setup and the number of sub-catchments and scenarios, we obtained 66 maps of SC. To analyse the spatial patterns of this information, we selected a series of aspects: I) the spatial location of the lowest and highest values of SC (based on percentiles); II) SC in the areas with the different burn severities; and III) SC in the different geomorphic features (crest, slope, foot-slope, embankment and stream channel). The crests corresponded to areas of

high slope gradient ($S > 55\%$) with small drainage areas ($A < 10,000 \text{ m}^2$); the slopes and foot-slopes had medium ($25\% < S < 55\%$) and lower ($S < 25\%$) slope gradients with small drainage areas. The stream channel corresponded to the cells with a drainage area higher than $10,000 \text{ m}^2$; and embankments were mapped in the LULC map (Sup. Fig. 3). The statistical analysis of the differences between scenarios within the same index and computation target was done by calculating the ANOVA with Tukey test (95% of confidence) on a random selection of 500 points. The same net was used for all comparisons.

2.6. Field measurements of sediment yield

In order to evaluate the indices output with independent values of sediment delivery after the fire, we estimated the values of sediment yield (SY ; Mg y^{-1}) and area specific sediment yield (SSY ; $\text{Mg ha}^{-1} \text{ y}^{-1}$) at the outlet of the three sub-catchments, where check-dams are located. The main characteristics of the check-dam construction and geometry are shown in Table 3. The SY and SSY were calculated by using the volume of sediments (VS ; m^3) retained by each check-dam, the bulk density of sediments (BD_{SED} ; Mg m^{-3}), the sediment trap efficiency (TE ; %) and the drainage area (A ; ha):

$$SY = \frac{SV \cdot BD_{SED}}{TE} \cdot 100 \quad (13)$$

$$SSY = \frac{SY}{A} \quad (14)$$

More details about TE in Mediterranean check-dams can be found in [Quiñonero-Rubio et al. \(2016\)](#). The field surveys to measure and collect sediments were done in July 2019. Detailed information about the check-dams built in the Sierra de Los Donceles can be found in [González-Romero et al. \(2019\)](#). Because the magnitude of SY depends on the upslope drainage area—larger catchments will produce higher amounts of sediments under the same soil erosion rates—the SSY is a suitable ratio to compare the hydrological response of the different sub-catchments. The SSY was defined by [Vanoni \(1975\)](#) as the total sediment outflow from a drainage basin or catchment area, measurable at a reference cross-section (in this study the check-dams) in a specific period of time (71.5, 68.5 and 70.0 months in this study). This ratio is commonly used in studies of soil erosion and sediment delivery to evaluate spatio-temporal changes and dynamics at different scales and under different land uses and management practices (e.g. [Rodríguez-Bachiller et al., 2019](#); [Zhang et al., 2019](#)).

3. Results

3.1. Hillslope-channel sediment connectivity

3.1.1. Estimated SC_{STREAM}

For the three sub-catchments, we obtained 33 maps of SC_{STREAM} using the four indices and evaluating the three temporal scenarios (Fig. 2). Three maps were obtained with each index, except with IC-C2016 that only considers topographic changes, and thus, two maps of

Table 2
Changes in the characteristics and mean values of some inputs during the three temporal scenarios and in the three sub-catchments.

Scenario	Dates	DEM	Trails	Rainfall	El ₃₀	C-RUSLE			Manning's n		
	(duration)	(LiDAR)	(n)	Condition	(MJ mm/ha h yr)	Sc.Pal	Sc.Ray	Sc.Con	Sc.Pal	Sc.Ray	Sc.Con
Pre-Fire	Jul2011-Jun2012 (1 yr)	Year 2009	3	Dry year	121.6	0.0408	0.0562	0.0482	0.0818	0.0559	0.0670
Fire	Jul2012-Jun2013 (1 yr)	Year 2009	3	Humid year	619.2	0.2402	0.3132	0.2917	0.0268	0.0336	0.0302
Post-Fire	Jul2014-Jun2015 (1 yr)	Year 2016	4	Humid year	1145.0	0.2009	0.1741	0.1882	0.0363	0.0360	0.0380

Table 3
Main characteristics of the check-dams in the three sub-catchments.

Sub-catchment	Construction			Check-dam			Sediment		
	ID	Company	Start date	End date	Height (m)	Width (m)	Volume (m ³)	TE (%)	SY (Mg y ⁻¹)
Sc.Pal	ELEVER	02/07/2013	30/07/2013	6.40	38.75	585.70	38.8	98.5	1.31
Sc.Ray	TRAGSA	10/10/2013	06/11/2013	6.45	36.00	389.52	55.3	71.4	1.96
Sc.Con	ELEVER	27/08/2013	16/09/2013	6.25	38.35	304.53	30.9	53.1	1.20

Fig. 2. Maps of sediment connectivity of the three temporal scenarios obtained with the four indices and considering the stream layer –channels– as the computation target (SC_{STREAM}).

SC_{STREAM} were generated by running this approach. Regarding the spatial patterns, we focussed the analysis on the areas with the highest (percentile 90) and lowest (percentile 10) values of SC_{STREAM} (Sup. Fig. 4). During the Pre-Fire scenario, 45% of the P90-pixels overlapped between the four indices and in the three sub-catchments (36% in Sc. Pal, 57% in Sc. Ray and 42% in Sc. Con), highlighting that the areas with the highest values of SC_{STREAM} were located near the streams. The remaining 55% P90-pixels also appeared near the streams with higher heterogeneity near the divides and very high homogeneity in the indices' predictions near the outlet. The overlapping of the P10-pixels between the four indices reached up to 40% of the total study area (40% in Sc. Pal, 36% in Sc. Ray and 44% in Sc. Con). Most overlapped P10-pixels appeared in the foot-slopes whereas the highest heterogeneity in the predictions of the areas with low SC_{STREAM} was located in different parts of the steep slopes but far from the crests.

In the maps of the Fire scenario, only 32% of the P90-pixels overlapped between the four indices (30% in Sc. Pal, 32% in Sc. Ray and 35% in Sc. Con), appearing the highest values of SC_{STREAM} in the streams and their surroundings. The remaining 68% P90-pixels also appeared near the streams and heterogeneity was more pronounced near the divides. The overlapping of the P10-pixels between the four indices reached up to 30% in the three sub-catchments (35% in Sc. Pal, 20% in Sc. Ray and 35% in Sc. Con). In the Post-Fire scenario, 44% of the P90-pixels overlapped between the four indices (38% in Sc. Pal, 51% in Sc. Ray and 43% in Sc. Con), whereas the overlapping of the P10-pixels between the four approaches reached up to 31% in the total study area (33% in Sc. Pal, 24% in Sc. Ray and 37% in Sc. Con). The overlapped and non-overlapped P-90 and P-10 pixels appeared roughly in the same areas in the three scenarios. Besides, no relation was observed between the location of the overlapped and non-overlapped areas and the location of the areas affected by the different burn severities.

The temporal changes of SC_{STREAM} were different –up to one order of magnitude– between the four indices (Fig. 3). The differences between the scenarios –and using the same index– were only significant with the IC-B2019 and AIC indices, in particular with the latest one (Table 4). Based on the Pre-Fire scenario, and taking into account the three sub-catchments, the average SC_{STREAM} increased 35% (33% in Sc. Pal, 37% in Sc. Ray and 36% in Sc. Con), 2% (2% in Sc. Pal, 1% in Sc. Ray and 2% in Sc. Con) and 42% (41% in Sc. Pal, 44% in Sc. Ray and 43% in Sc. Con) in the Fire scenario with the IC-B2019, IC-P and AIC indices, respectively. Contradictory results appeared in the Post-Fire scenario among the indices output and compared with the Fire scenario: The SC_{STREAM} decreased –11% (–2% in Sc. Pal, –19% in Sc. Ray and –13% in Sc. Con), –0.5% (–0.2% in Sc. Pal, –0.4% in Sc. Ray and –0.9% in Sc. Con) and –0.2% (+0.2% in Sc. Pal, +0.1% in Sc. Ray and –0.9% in Sc. Con) with the IC-B2019, IC-C2016 and IC-P indices, respectively; and increased +5% (+11% in Sc. Pal, +1% in Sc. Ray and +4% in Sc. Con) with the AIC index.

Table 4

Mean values of estimated sediment connectivity with the four indices in the three temporal scenarios and using the two computation targets. Different lowercase letters in bold type in the same line and computation target indicates the difference between temporal scenarios was significant at 0.05 level.

Index	Stream target			Outlet target		
	Pre-Fire	Fire	Post-Fire	Pre-Fire	Fire	Post-Fire
IC-B2019	–4.930 a	–3.415 b	–3.405 b	–5.704 a	–4.236 c	–4.695 b
IC-C2016	–3.329 a	–3.329 a	–3.731 a	–3.801 a	–3.801 a	–4.091 b
IC-P	–2.163 a	–2.035 a	–2.407 a	–2.642 a	–2.620 a	–2.730 b
AIC	–7.404 a	–4.354 b	–4.021 c	–7.734 a	–4.708 c	–5.152 b

In the analysis on the unburned and burned (three burn severity classes) areas, the values of SC_{STREAM} showed clear differences among the indices and between the classes (Table 5). During the Fire scenario, the average SC_{STREAM} within the burned area increased 35%, 2% and 42% with the IC-B2019, IC-P and AIC, respectively. Only the IC-P showed increasing changes of SC_{STREAM} with increasing burn severities, whereas the IC-B2019 and AIC were not responsive to the severity classes. In the Post-Fire scenario, the values of SC_{STREAM} decreased –7%, –1% and –0.1% with the IC-B2019, IC-C2016 and IC-P, respectively; and increased +8% with the AIC. For each scenario, the highest values of SC_{STREAM} appeared in the areas affected by moderate-low severity, whereas the areas affected by high severity had lower values of SC_{STREAM} than those areas affected by moderate-high severity. In the two unburned areas of Sc. Pal, the estimated changes followed –in general– the same pattern as that described above although with different magnitudes that were lower during the Fire scenario and higher during the Post-Fire scenario. SC changed in the unburned areas due to their spatial location, surrounded by burned areas, and thus, the fire effect in the up-slope areas that drainage over the unburned areas affected the SC values in the unburned areas.

3.1.2. Estimated SC_{STREAM} in the geomorphic features

As expected, the highest average values of SC_{STREAM} were found in the outlets and stream systems in the three temporal scenarios and with the four approaches (Table 6). The embankments also had high values, but clearly lower than those obtained in the streams and outlets. The foot-slopes had the lowest values of SC_{STREAM} in all cases. The differences between the values of SC_{STREAM} in the crests and steep slopes were very low with higher values in the crests with the IC-B2019, IC-P and AIC and higher values in the steep slopes with the IC-C2016. Regarding the temporal changes, the values of SC_{STREAM} increased in the six geomorphic features during the Fire scenario –based on the Pre-Fire scenario– appearing the highest differences in the stream systems and outlets. During the Post-Fire scenario, the changes were more heterogeneous appearing some areas with higher values of SC_{STREAM} and

Fig. 3. Evolution of the estimated sediment connectivity (mean \pm sd values), using the stream layer as computation target (SC_{STREAM}), in the three sub-catchments and using the four selected indices.

Table 5

Average mean values of SC_{STREAM} in the areas affected under different burn severity obtained in the three sub-catchments with the four indices. The percentages indicate the changes within each index related to the previous temporal scenario.

Scenario	Index	Burn severity class			
		Unburned	Mod.-Low sev.	Mod.-High sev.	High severity
Pre-Fire	IC-B2019	-6.685	-3.918	-4.730	-5.092
	IC-C2016	-4.469	-2.879	-3.073	-3.163
	IC-P	-3.689	-1.527	-1.955	-2.040
	AIC	-8.658	-6.610	-7.284	-7.592
Fire	IC-B2019	-6.155 (+8%)	-2.530 (+35%)	-3.077 (+35%)	-3.372 (+34%)
	IC-C2016	-4.469 (NC)	-2.879 (NC)	-3.073 (NC)	-3.163 (NC)
	IC-P	-3.693 (-0.1%)	-1.516 (+0.7%)	-1.914 (+2.1%)	-1.977 (+3.1%)
	AIC	-6.711 (+22%)	-3.809 (+42%)	-4.216 (+42%)	-4.459 (+41%)
Post-Fire	IC-B2019	-4.965 (+19%)	-2.732 (-8%)	-3.372 (-10%)	-3.446 (-2%)
	IC-C2016	-4.468 (+0.03%)	-2.897 (-0.6%)	-3.086 (-0.4%)	-3.179 (-0.5%)
	IC-P	-3.643 (+1.4%)	-1.501 (+1.0%)	-1.918 (-0.2%)	-2.001 (-1.2%)
	AIC	-4.991 (+26%)	-3.478 (+9%)	-3.974 (+6%)	-3.992 (+10%)

NC: No change.

other with lower values in the same map and compared with the Fire scenario. Again, the highest changes appeared in the outlet and stream systems.

3.2. Hillslope-outlet sediment connectivity

3.2.1. Estimated SC_{OUTLET}

In the same way as for the previous maps of SC_{STREAM} , we obtained eleven maps of SC_{OUTLET} for each sub-catchment (Fig. 4). Again, three maps were obtained with each index, except with IC-C2016 that only considers topographic changes, and thus, two maps of SC_{OUTLET} were generated by running this approach. The first clear difference between the maps of SC_{STREAM} and SC_{OUTLET} was the spatial distribution of the values of SC. In general, the histograms of the maps of SC_{STREAM} were asymmetric and bimodal with sharp peaks whereas the histograms of

the maps of SC_{OUTLET} were unimodal, broader-based and symmetric (Sup. Fig. 5).

Regarding the percentiles of the SC_{OUTLET} maps and during the Pre-Fire scenario, only 36% of the P90-pixels overlapped between the four indices in the three sub-catchments (30% in Sc.Pal, 41% in Sc.Ray and 36% in Sc.Con), appearing the highest values of SC_{OUTLET} in the stream systems and surrounding the outlets (Sup. Fig. 6). The remaining 64% P90-pixels appeared near the stream systems and in the embankments. The overlapping of the P10-pixels between the four indices was low and only reached up to 22% of the total study area (21% in Sc.Pal, 28% in Sc. Ray and 19% in Sc.Con). Most of the overlapped and non-overlapped pixels appeared in the foot-slopes but heterogeneously distributed.

In the maps of the Fire scenario, 39% of the P90-pixels overlapped between the four indices (35% in Sc.Pal, 42% in Sc.Ray and 40% in Sc. Con), appearing the highest values of SC_{OUTLET} in the same areas as those observed in the Pre-Fire scenario. The overlapping of the P10-

Table 6

Average values of SC_{STREAM} obtained in the different geomorphic features of the three sub-catchments. The percentages indicate the changes within each index related to the previous temporal scenario.

Scenario	Index	Geomorphic feature					
		Crest	Slope	Foot-slope	Embankment	Stream	Outlet
Pre-Fire	IC-B2019	-4.240	-4.548	-5.545	-3.136	-1.974	-1.084
	IC-C2016	-3.005	-2.919	-3.562	-2.315	-0.313	+0.692
	IC-P	-1.668	-1.749	-2.632	-1.195	+0.804	+1.762
	AIC	-7.044	-7.187	-7.770	-5.366	-4.508	-3.209
Fire	IC-B2019	-2.645 (+38%)	-2.881 (+37%)	-3.900 (+30%)	-2.213 (+29%)	-1.207 (+39%)	+0.520 (+148%)
	IC-C2016	-3.005 (NC)	-2.919 (NC)	-3.562 (NC)	-2.315 (NC)	-0.313 (NC)	+0.692 (NC)
	IC-P	-1.628 (+2%)	-1.697 (+3%)	-2.573 (+2%)	-1.202 (-1%)	-0.007 (+101%)	+1.768 (+0.3%)
	AIC	-4.034 (+43%)	-4.105 (+43%)	-4.712 (+39%)	-3.029 (+44%)	-2.279 (+49%)	-0.191 (+94%)
Post-Fire	IC-B2019	-3.025 (-14%)	-3.179 (-10%)	-3.984 (-2%)	-2.260 (-2%)	-1.085 (+10%)	+0.071 (-86%)
	IC-C2016	-3.027 (-1%)	-2.941 (-1%)	-3.537 (+1%)	-2.332 (-1%)	-0.800 (-156%)	+0.076 (-89%)
	IC-P	-1.640 (-1%)	-1.720 (-1%)	-2.559 (+1%)	-1.157 (+4%)	+0.358 (+5183%)	+1.202 (-32%)
	AIC	-3.877 (+4%)	-3.865 (+6%)	-4.261 (+10%)	-2.549 (+16%)	-1.640 (+28%)	-0.238 (-24%)

NC: No change.

Fig. 4. Maps of sediment connectivity of the three temporal scenarios obtained with the four indices and considering the check-dams as the computation target (SC_{OUTLET}).

pixels between the four indices was only of 22% in the three sub-catchments (19% in Sc.Pal, 27% in Sc.Ray and 20% in Sc.Con). The overlapped and non-overlapped pixels appeared in the same areas as those areas in the Pre-Fire scenario. In the Post-Fire scenario, 37% of the P90-pixels overlapped between the four indices (34% in Sc.Pal, 32% in Sc.Ray and 46% in Sc.Con), mirroring the same spatial patterns as those drawn in the Pre-Fire and Fire scenarios. The overlapping of the P10-pixels between the four indices was very low and only reached up to 18% in the total study area (13% in Sc.Pal, 25% in Sc.Ray and 18% in Sc.Con) showing the highest homogeneity near the divides and some

sections of the trails. The highest heterogeneity was found in different areas of the foot-slopes.

The temporal changes of SC_{OUTLET} were similar to those obtained with the SC_{STREAM} , but the magnitude was smaller (Fig. 5). The differences between the scenarios –and using the same index– were significant with the four indices, showing the IC-B2019 and AIC indices the highest differences (Table 4). Based on the Pre-Fire scenario, and taking into account the three sub-catchments, the average SC_{OUTLET} increased 25% (24% in Sc.Pal, 26% in Sc.Ray and 26% in Sc.Con), 1% (1% in Sc.Pal, 1% in Sc.Ray and 1% in Sc.Con) and 34% (33% in Sc.Pal, 35% in Sc.Ray

Fig. 5. Evolution of the estimated sediment connectivity (mean ± sd values), using the outlet (check-dam) as the computation target (SC_{OUTLET}), in the three sub-catchments and using the four selected indices.

and 34% in Sc.Con) in the Fire scenario with the IC-B2019, IC-P and AIC indices, respectively. In the Post-Fire scenario, and compared with the Fire scenario, the SC_{OUTLET} decreased -7% (-1% in Sc.Pal, -12% in Sc. Ray and -7% in Sc.Con), -1.0% (-0.6% in Sc.Pal, -2.9% in Sc.Ray and +0.4% in Sc.Con) and -1.4% (-0.4% in Sc.Pal, -4.3% in Sc.Ray and +0.6% in Sc.Con) with the IC-B2019, IC-C2016 and IC-P indices, respectively, and increased +4% (+7% in Sc.Pal, +0.1% in Sc.Ray and +4% in Sc.Con) with the AIC.

The relative values of SC_{OUTLET} among the areas affected by different burn severity classes, and their temporal changes (Table 7), were comparable to those obtained with the SC_{STREAM} although the magnitude of the changes was smaller between the Fire and Pre-Fire scenarios (-24% on average between SC_{OUTLET} and SC_{STREAM}) and almost equal between the Post-Fire and Fire scenarios (-2% on average between SC_{OUTLET} and SC_{STREAM}). During the Fire scenario, the average SC_{OUTLET} in the three sub-catchments increased 25%, 1% and 34% with the IC-B2019, IC-P and AIC, respectively. Only the IC-P showed increasing changes of SC_{OUTLET} with increasing burn severities, whereas the IC-B2019 and AIC were not responsive to the severity classes. In the Post-Fire scenario, the values of SC_{OUTLET} decreased -4%, -0.4% and -0.1% with the IC-B2019, IC-C2016 and IC-P, respectively, and increased 6% with the AIC. Before and after the fire, the highest values of SC_{OUTLET} appeared in

the areas affected by moderate-low severity, and the areas affected by high severity had lower values of SC_{OUTLET} than those areas affected by moderate-high severity. In the unburned areas, the estimated changes followed - in general - the same pattern as that described above, but with a lower magnitude during the Fire scenario and more marked during the Post-Fire scenario.

3.2.2. Estimated SC_{OUTLET} in the geomorphic features

The average values of SC_{OUTLET} in the different geomorphic features were lower than those obtained in the same features with the SC_{STREAM} maps, except in the outlets where -as expected- the values with the two computation targets were almost the same (Table 8). The values of SC_{OUTLET} in the different features followed the same order as that obtained with the SC_{STREAM} maps: Foot-slopes < steep slopes (5% higher SC than in the previous feature) < crests (3% higher) < embankments (0.04% higher) < streams (25% higher) < outlets (97% higher). Regarding the temporal changes, the values of SC_{OUTLET} increased in the six geomorphic features in the Fire scenario, appearing the highest differences in the outlets (+136% on average) and moderate differences in the other features (between +17% and +26%). In the Post-Fire scenario, the changes were more heterogeneous appearing lower values of SC_{OUTLET} in the six features with the IC-B2019 and IC-P, in five features

Table 7

Average mean values of SC_{OUTLET} in the areas affected under different burn severity obtained in the three sub-catchments with the four indices. The percentages indicate the changes within each index related to the previous temporal scenario.

Scenario	Index	Burn severity class			
		Unburned	Mod.-Low sev.	Mod.-High sev.	High severity
Pre-Fire	IC-B2019	-7.240	-6.019	-6.698	-6.961
	IC-C2016	-5.048	-4.683	-4.927	-4.978
	IC-P	-4.249	-3.491	-3.901	-3.968
	AIC	-9.230	-8.496	-9.090	-9.323
Fire	IC-B2019	-6.464	-4.517	-5.040	-5.268
		(+11%)	(+25%)	(+25%)	(+24%)
	IC-C2016	-5.048	-4.683	-4.927	-4.978
		(NC)	(NC)	(NC)	(NC)
	IC-P	-4.227	-3.474	-3.861	-3.918
		(+0.5%)	(+0.5%)	(+1.0%)	(+1.3%)
	AIC	-7.033	-5.581	-6.019	-6.216
		(+24%)	(+34%)	(+34%)	(+33%)
Post-Fire	IC-B2019	-5.628	-4.757	-5.300	-5.359
		(+13%)	(-5%)	(-5%)	(-2%)
	IC-C2016	-5.138	-4.668	-4.963	-5.013
		(-1.8%)	(+0.3%)	(-0.7%)	(-0.7%)
	IC-P	-4.299	-3.431	-3.894	-3.948
		(-1.7%)	(+1.2%)	(-0.9%)	(-0.8%)
	AIC	-5.678	-5.286	-5.748	-5.779
		(+19%)	(+5%)	(+5%)	(+7%)

NC: No change.

Table 8
Average values of SC_{OUTLET} obtained in the different geomorphic features of the three sub-catchments. The percentages indicate the changes within each index related to the previous temporal scenario.

Scenario	Index	Geomorphic feature					
		Crest	Slope	Foot-slope	Embankment	Stream	Outlet
Pre-Fire	IC-B2019	-6.346	-6.634	-7.070	-6.129	-4.979	-1.084
	IC-C2016	-4.824	-4.864	-5.126	-4.887	-3.271	-0.545
	IC-P	-3.656	-3.810	-4.216	-3.893	-2.215	+0.549
	AIC	-8.910	-9.081	-9.240	-8.272	-7.370	-3.209
Fire	IC-B2019	-4.723	-4.972	-5.434	-4.941	-3.352	+0.520
		(+26%)	(+25%)	(+23%)	(+19%)	(+33%)	(+148%)
	IC-C2016	-4.824	-4.864	-5.126	-4.887	-3.271	-0.545
		(NC)	(NC)	(NC)	(NC)	(NC)	(NC)
	IC-P	-3.622	-3.770	-4.176	-3.858	-2.177	+1.768
		(+1%)	(+1%)	(+1%)	(+1%)	(+2%)	(+222%)
	AIC	-5.873	-6.006	-6.189	-5.671	-4.329	-0.191
		(+34%)	(+34%)	(+33%)	(+31%)	(+41%)	(+94%)
Post-Fire	IC-B2019	-5.030	-5.220	-5.554	-5.134	-4.130	+0.210
		(-6%)	(-5%)	(-2%)	(-4%)	(-23%)	(-60%)
	IC-C2016	-4.838	-4.895	-5.153	-4.963	-3.822	+0.076
		(-0.3%)	(-1%)	(-1%)	(-2%)	(-17%)	(+114%)
	IC-P	-3.623	-3.795	-4.201	-3.925	-2.737	+1.202
		(-0.02%)	(-1%)	(-1%)	(-2%)	(-26%)	(-32%)
	AIC	-5.649	-5.722	-5.780	-5.336	-4.545	-0.101
		(+4%)	(+5%)	(+7%)	(+6%)	(-5%)	(+47%)

NC: No change.

–except the outlets– with IC-C2016 and higher values of SC_{OUTLET} with the AIC in all the features except in the streams. These results highlighted the complexity and heterogeneity of the estimated spatial patterns with the four indices and their temporal changes.

3.2.3. Measured sediment yield at the three check-dams

The three sub-catchments showed comparable erosive dynamics with SSY ranging between 1.20 (Sc.Con) and 1.96 (Sc.Ray) $Mg\ ha^{-1}\ y^{-1}$ (Table 3). Sc.Ray, with the highest SSY , has the smallest drainage area and the highest mean slope gradient.

4. Discussion

4.1. Differences between the spatial patterns and temporal changes

The different frequency distribution of the SC values was directly related to the two computation targets. The histograms of the SC_{STREAM} maps reflected the complex hydrological response of the soil when the channels were considered as the target, whereas the average hydrological response of the whole sub-catchment was reflected with the SC_{OUTLET} maps. Schopper et al. (2019) also found after running the IC-Cavalli in a large catchment located in the Italian Alps that the SC_{OUTLET} map put more emphasis on the incised network, while SC_{STREAM} map focused on slopes and less on incisions and thus the SC_{STREAM} approach appeared as a better suited option for interpreting the hillslope-channel connectivity. This aspect of the computation setup explains the lower values of SC obtained in the different geomorphic features, except at the outlet, with the SC_{OUTLET} maps than with the SC_{STREAM} maps for the same temporal scenario and index.

In general, the highest homogeneity between the different indices' predictions appeared in the Pre-Fire scenario (overlapping between the SC_{STREAM} maps: 40% in P10-pixels and 45% in P90-pixels; and between the SC_{OUTLET} maps: 22% in P10-pixels and 36% in P90-pixels) whereas the highest heterogeneity was obtained in the Fire scenario with SC_{STREAM} (overlapping: 30% in P10-pixels and 32% in P90-pixels) and in the Post-Fire scenario with SC_{OUTLET} (overlapping: 18% in P10-pixels and 37% in P90-pixels). These results agreed with the patterns of spatial and temporal changes of soil erosion and deposition observed by Brogan et al. (2019) in two watersheds in the first 2 years after burning (intense hydrological response) and over the subsequent 2 years

(only minor changes). In our case, the fire and post-fire practices added many disturbances on the original forest conditions that implied more complex input layers, such as Murphy et al. (2019) did to model post-fire sediment cascades combining several models and network-scale sediment routing. On average, and considering the three scenarios, the overlapping of the P10- and P90-pixels between the SC_{OUTLET} maps (ca. 21% in P10 and 37% in P90) was lower than between the SC_{STREAM} maps (ca. 34% in P10 and 41% in P90). This result may be related with the net sediment accumulation that occurs more frequent in the valley bottoms during low intensity rainfall events that do not activate all catchment compartments, resulting in a higher sedimentological response heterogeneity (Schnabel et al., 2018). As said above, SC_{STREAM} was representative of the hillslope sediment connectivity of the different small sub-basins that can be distinguished upslope from all the pixels that constitute the stream systems. In that way, the flow path lengths of the different sub-basins were comparable among them, resulting on a higher spatial homogeneity. Nevertheless, the SC_{OUTLET} maps represented the hydrological response of the whole sub-catchment in a longer time-lapse and thus the differences among the distinct sub-basins became more relevant between the four indices. When targeting the outlet, the connectivity patterns predicted by the different indices had meaningful differences, which talked of the complexity of long-term predictions. Therefore, the SC_{STREAM} maps may be linked to the intense episodes defined as those within which all eroded soils are transported out the sub-basins without deposition during a hydrological event (Gao and Puckett, 2012).

The temporal changes of SC_{STREAM} and SC_{OUTLET} between the three scenarios were different in the four indices (Table 4). The different type and number of inputs explained this distinct behaviour. Indices that include the RUSLE C-Factor (IC-B2019 and AIC) were sensitive to the fire perturbation on the vegetation, and thus, their values of SC clearly increased in the Fire scenario. This result agree with that presented by Vieira et al. (2018) after doing a multiple regression model analysis to identify the key factors that influence the erosive response in a burned Mediterranean forest, finding that ground cover variables were more relevant than other factors, such as soil water repellency and soil moisture. In the Post-Fire scenario, the IC-B2019 and AIC showed different trends. The IC-B2019 values slightly decreased reflecting the vegetation recovery of the Post-Fire scenario. On the other hand, the AIC values kept rising, which came as a result of the

aggregation of the different factors considered by this index. More specifically the key factor that explained this different trend was the rainfall erosivity (R_f) which was the highest at the Post-Fire scenario. Despite the inputs of the four indices reflected the fire and post-fire practices induced temporal changes on the vegetation and topographic factors, the AIC was the approach that considered the highest number of factors with temporal changes. Cucchiari et al. (2019) also highlighted the relevance of estimating functional SC instead of generating maps of structural SC that cannot reflect the actual dynamics of sediment transport.

Regarding the IC-C2016 values, the slight decrease observed in the Post-Fire scenario can be explained by the role played by the new skid trails and hillslope measures made during the post-fire management practices. The effect of trails and forest roads on the overland flow pathways is complex: I) favouring in some sections the occurrence of concentrated flow and lateral connections between different hillslope sectors; II) disconnecting the upslope and downslope sectors where the overland flows along the trail; and III) promoting higher SC within the stream system downslope from the outlet of the trail (Lana-Renault et al., 2018). The IC-P did not result a very sensitive index to the temporal changes due to the similar values of the Manning's n roughness for the three scenarios. This resulted in similar values of the W factor and for the final index output. Further research should be focused on two aspects, namely: I) refining the assessment of the n values for fire-affected areas; and II) testing alternative approaches, such as roughness height, overland flow velocity or travel time (López-Vicente and Navas, 2010). Overall, these results revealed the limitations of the approaches IC-C2016, IC-P and IC-B2019 to explain the complex and dynamic processes of soil erosion and sediment transport which take place in a burned area, especially in the first years after the fire (Brogan et al., 2019; Murphy et al., 2019). Meanwhile AIC by considering a larger number of factors could explain these processes in a more accurate way.

4.2. Indices performance regarding fire severities

Although temporal changes on SC were observed with the four indices, and IC-B2019 and AIC showed marked differences between de Pre-Fire and Fire scenarios, none of the four indices were significantly sensitive to the different burn severities. This result can be considered as a shortcoming of the four indices because some studies have reported that those areas affected more severely by a fire presented higher values of surface runoff and sediment detachment and transport (Moody and Martin, 2009). In our study, those areas classified as “high severity” did not show the highest SC_{STREAM} or SC_{OUTLET} values, which corresponded to moderate and low severities. This apparently contradictory result can be explained attending to the geomorphological features of the studied catchments, in particular the slope gradient, which have a strong influence on connectivity (Persichillo et al., 2018). The high severity areas mainly corresponded with the foot-slopes, where the predominance of pine forest and scrubland led into a more intense fire, meanwhile those areas cataloged as moderate and low affected matched with upper parts (crests and steep-slopes) where the main fuel were mostly herbaceous plants. Foot-slopes were the geomorphic feature with the lowest SC_{STREAM} and SC_{OUTLET} values. This fact can be explained because the gentle slopes in these areas act as long-term depositional-prone places, and thus, temporal sediment storage and effective sediment transport takes place through the channels (Estrany et al., 2016; Murphy et al., 2019). Martínez-Murillo and López-Vicente (2018) already reported that other factors like logging had a greater influence on connectivity in the hillslope-catchment system than burn severity. The IC-C2016, IC-P only predicted important changes on SC in the channels and outlets, where almost no change was estimated in the remaining geomorphic features (Tables 6 and 8). These results can be considered as a serious limitation of the two approaches to assess fire-induced changes on SC at hillslope scale.

4.3. Indices performance related to the stored sediment at the three check-dams

The calculated SSY had a similar scale to the sediment yield measured by Romero et al. (2007, 2012), Boix-Fayos et al. (2007), Sougnez et al. (2011) or Bellin et al. (2011) in studies carried out in other Spanish areas under similar physiographic and climatic conditions. Even though the SC_{STREAM} and SC_{OUTLET} values for each sub-catchment were quite similar for the four indices, Sc.Ray was the one with the highest values for all of them. Bellin et al. (2011) observed that the drainage area had a strong negative effect on SSY , owing to the more frequent presence of local sediment storages within the larger catchments. Likewise, the largest increment of SC in the Fire scenario was obtained in Sc.Ray with the IC-B2019 and AIC –that were the most suitable indices– with both the SC_{STREAM} and SC_{OUTLET} maps, whereas lower and similar increments of SC appeared in the other two sub-catchments that also presented very similar and lower values of SSY (Fig. 6). This means that the largest changes in estimated SC appeared in the catchments with the highest SSY , and this pattern was especially true with the IC-B2019 and AIC.

4.4. Implications for post-fire management

In Spain, check-dam construction after fires has been a widespread measure in the last decades to reduce sediment yield and prevent mudflow downslope. Nonetheless, the efficiency of this measure has been widely contested by several authors for being considered a short-term solution with high economic cost (Quiñonero-Rubio et al., 2016), which has effects on channel morphology and causes erosion downstream (Boix-Fayos et al., 2008). Prioritizing the construction of low impact measures at hillslope scale over large check-dams must be considered, in the same way as Albert-Belda et al. (2019), who installed Easy-Barriers© on steep terrains affected by fires as a quick, low-cost solution to decrease the peak flow, the loss of seeds and induce a delay in the runoff time at the outlet. Gómez-Sánchez et al. (2019) also proposed log erosion barriers and contour-felled log debris, which were proved efficient to retain sediments and limit nutrient losses from hillslopes, resulting in a better vegetation recovery.

An optimum placement of check-dams and other measures seems crucial to improve its effectiveness and an optimal use of manager's resources (Castillo et al., 2007). This aspect highlights the importance of understanding connectivity patterns at catchment scale and how fire affects sediment exportation. For that purpose, connectivity indices sensitive to changes induced by fires, such as the IC-B2019 and AIC, look like a crucial management tool to be considered in the future. Computation target is also a key factor to take into account, depending on the dominant erosive processes in the study catchment. Since check-dams are emergency measures that commonly get silted in the first years after fire, the assessment of SC_{STREAM} in areas with few intense rainfall events may be more suitable in order to predict sediment transport after fire and better place this type of infrastructures.

5. Conclusions

This study successfully evaluated the effect of a forest fire and post-fire practices (salvage logging, skid trails and check dams) on the sediment connectivity dynamic at catchment scale using four different indices (IC-Borselli, IC-Cavalli, IC-Persichillo and AIC) and field observations and measurements (geomorphic features, burn severity classes and estimated sediment yield rates at check-dams). For the three defined temporal scenarios (before the fire, one year just after the fire and two years after the fire) and the two computation targets (streams: hillslope-channel SC; and check-dams: hillslope-outlet SC), our results demonstrated that the Borselli's and AIC indexes were the most appropriate approaches to study sediment connectivity in a Mediterranean

Fig. 6. Relationship between the changes of estimated sediment connectivity (ΔSC ; %) at each sub-catchment between the Fire and Pre-Fire scenarios obtained with the four indices and the measured values of area specific sediment yield (SSY ; $Mg\ ha^{-1}\ yr^{-1}$) in the check-dam of each sub-catchment.

mountainous fire-affected area. However, it is worth noting that Borselli's index did not reflect the effect of rainfall erosivity, which is important to assess actual sediment dynamics. The Cavalli and Persichillo indexes were not an appropriate approach for evaluating sediment connectivity changes. The Cavalli's index was only sensitive to topographic changes (skid trails). Moreover, and in spite of being not a good approach, the Persichillo index was the only approach that was sensitive to the different burn severity classes.

The different frequency distribution of the SC values was directly related to the user-defined computation targets. The histograms of the SC_{STREAM} maps, in particular those obtained with the Borselli's and AIC indexes, reflected the complex hydrological response of the soil when the stream systems were considered as the target, whereas the average hydrological response of the whole sub-catchment was reflected with the SC_{OUTLET} maps. The SC_{OUTLET} maps put more emphasis on the incised network, while the SC_{STREAM} maps appeared as a better suited option for interpreting the hillslope-channel connectivity. This aspect of the computation setup explains the lower values of SC obtained in the different geomorphic features, except at the outlet, with the SC_{OUTLET} maps than with the SC_{STREAM} maps for the same temporal scenario and index. Thus, the overlay between the fire severities and the geomorphic features appeared as a key aspect to better understand the indices outputs using both the stream and outlet targets.

In relation to the studied sub-catchments, the largest increment of the sediment connectivity for the Fire scenario was obtained in Sc.Rayares (the smallest studied watershed with 66 ha) with the IC-B2019 and AIC index, and for both the SC_{STREAM} and SC_{OUTLET} maps. Lower increments of sediment connectivity were found in the other two sub-catchments (Conejo and Palomar with 143 and 194 ha, respectively), which also presented very similar values of SSY . Thus, we found a good and positive agreement between the SSY and the changes in SC due to the fire. Regarding the two targets, our results showed that the SC_{STREAM} assessment may be more suitable for fire affected Mediterranean areas with low-frequency intense rainfall events in order to predict effective and long-distance sediment transport. Overall, this work provides an interesting evaluation of different connectivity indexes for assessing sediment connectivity in Mediterranean forest ecosystems affected by fires and with subsequent post-fire managing strategies across temporal and spatial scales and between geomorphic systems.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

M. López-Vicente: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Validation, Supervision. **J. González-Romero:** Conceptualization, Formal analysis. **M.E. Lucas-Borja:** Conceptualization, Validation, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version, at doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.139206>. These data include the Google map of the most important areas described in this article.

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